

Actual vs Predicted (MinUV)

Standardized Residuals (MinUV)

Partial Regression Plot (MinUV)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.3592$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 1.1550

p-value: 0.2825

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 5.9911

df: 2

p-value: 0.0500

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (MinUV)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – MinUV

